

Changes in urea N remaining at deep placement sites after application of SCU in a wetland soil. Ludhiana, India, 1988.

capacity/100 g. A nylon screen bag with 460 mg N as SCU (38.6% N) was placed between 2 layers of wet soil freshly collected from the lower layer of 3- × 5-cm or six 20- × 10 cm rice hills 5 d after transplanting of 45-d-old seedlings of cultivar PR106. The plots received a basal dose of 26 kg P and 50 kg K/ha. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design.

Five nylon bags from each treatment were chosen at random and SCU granules were digested, then analyzed for urea N at 6, 10, 25, 45, and 60 d after placement. The remaining wet soil mass was extracted with 2 M KCl-PMA solution, and the extract was also analyzed for urea N.

Results showed that SCU granules released urea N at a fairly controlled rate up to 60 d after placement. Spacing significantly affected the amounts of SCU N recovered. SCU N disappeared faster in the closer plant spacing (see figure). Closer plant spacing had more impact after 30 d of SCU placement, coinciding with active proliferation of rice roots. Furthermore, dissolution rate of SCU was about 9 and 19% higher than its empirical 7-d dissolution rate of 21% with 15- × 20-cm and 20- × 10-cm spacings, respectively. □

Effect of azolla and other fertilizers on rice yields

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We evaluated azolla as an organic manure, varying application rate and percentage of substitution for chemical fertilizer at RARS Pattambi during rabi seasons (Sep-Jan) of 1980 and 1981.

In the split-plot experiment, azolla at 5.0, 7.5, and 10.0 t/ha was compared with cattle manure and green leaves

(*Gliricidia maculata*) at 5 t/ha. Subplot treatment was the percentage of fertilizer dose (90:45:45 kg NPK/ha) applied. The sandy loam soil contained 0.02% available N, 9.7 kg available P, and 184.4 kg K with a pH of 5.5. On dry weight basis, cattle manure has 9.4% dry matter, 1.52% N, 0.4% P, and 21.1% K; for gliricidia, the values are 21.1, 2.6, 0.5, and 1.4%.

Substituting 5 t azolla/ha for cattle manure saved 25% of the fertilizer dose (see table). Azolla at 7.5 t/ha with full dose of fertilizer recorded the highest grain and straw yields. Applying more than 7.5 t azolla/ha was not beneficial. □

Effect of organic manures and fertilizer levels on grain yield of rice. Pattambi, India, 1980 and 1981 rabi (Sep-Jan).

Organic manure	Rate (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha) with given fertilizer dose ^a				
		0	25%	50%	75%	100%
Control	0	1.8	2.3	2.7	3.1	3.6
Cattle manure	5.0	2.4	2.7	3.1	3.1	3.6
Green leaves	5.0	2.8	3.1	3.4	3.6	3.8
Azolla	5.0	2.1	2.7	2.8	3.4	3.7
Azolla	7.5	2.6	3.0	3.2	3.7	4.2
Azolla	10.0	2.3	2.8	3.2	3.2	3.7
<i>F</i> test ^b		*				
LSD (0.05)		0.27 ^c	0.29 ^d			

^aFertilizer dose: 90-45-45 kg NPK/ha. ^bSignificant at 0.05 level. ^cFor comparing 2 fertilizer levels at the same level of organic manure. ^dFor comparing 2 organic manures at the same or different levels of fertilizer.

Effects of seedling age and zinc application on yield of rice

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We evaluated the impact of seedling age and Zn application on rice in wet season, using three seedling ages as main plots, five rates of Zn applied through soil and one foliar spray as subplots, with three replications (see table). Seedlings (30, 40, and 50 d old) of variety Pant Dhan 4 were transplanted at 2-3 seedlings/hill, 20- × 20-cm spacing. Soil was Beni silty clay loam, fine silty, mixed, hyperthermic, Aquic

Hapludoll with pH 7.6, CEC 20 meq/100 g, 1.0% organic C, 20 kg available (Olsen) P/ha, and 0.8 ppm Zn.

Grain yield declined significantly with increasing seedling age (see table). Panicles/m² and filled grains/panicle were significantly higher with 30- and 40-d-old seedlings than with 50-d-old ones. Filled grain percentage and 1,000-grain weight were significantly higher with 30- and 40-d-old seedlings than with 50-d-old ones.

Application of 8 ppm Zn gave significantly higher yield than other Zn treatments; 4 ppm Zn was significantly superior to Zn spray, 1 ppm Zn, and the control. Panicles/m², filled grains/panicle, and filled grains percentage were significantly higher with 8 ppm Zn than with all other